

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D9.6

Final communications and dissemination delivery

 <https://xrotor-project.eu>

 @XROTORProject

April 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007135

Document Information

Deliverable ID	9.6
Deliverable Title	Final communications and dissemination delivery
Lead beneficiary	University of Strathclyde
Contributing beneficiaries	University College Cork
Due date Annex I	2024.04.30
Issue date	2024.04.30
Dissemination level	Public
Author(s)	James Carroll (UoS), Niall Dunphy (UCC)

Approval

Version	Date	Description	Reviewed by	Approved by
1	2024.04.30		William Leithead & James Carroll 	

Copyright

© 2024 X-ROTOR Consortium

The X-Rotor Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101007135. For more information on the project, its partners, and contributors please see <https://xrotor-project.eu>.

Disclaimer

The information contained in this document represents the views of X-ROTOR consortium as of the date they are published. The X-ROTOR consortium does not guarantee that any information contained herein is error-free, or up to date, nor makes warranties, express, implied, or statutory, by publishing this document. The information in this document is provided as is and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Commission nor its executive agencies are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

X-ROTOR Consortium

University of Strathclyde

Delft University of Technology

University College Cork – National University of Ireland, Cork

Fundacion Cener

General Electric Renovables España

Norwegian University of Science and Technology

CENER

NTNU – Trondheim
Norwegian University of
Science and Technology

UCC
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh, Éire
University College Cork, Ireland

<https://xrotor-project.eu>

Table of Contents

About X-ROTOR	5
1 Introduction	7
1.1 Background	7
2 Communication tools	8
2.1 Website	8
2.2 Briefing Statement	9
2.3 Logos	9
2.4 Press release guidelines	10
2.5 Presentation template	11
2.6 Display banner poster	12
3 Dissemination Outputs	13

About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This brief report provides a final report on the communication and dissemination of the project and its activities.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OREC	Ocean Renewable Energy Coalition
WESC	Wind Energy Science Conference
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

This document presents an overview of the work undertaken to develop material to communicate the project’s results and disseminate the project results and outputs. In effect it constitutes a report on the implementation of the dissemination and communications strategy, with a focus on results and outputs. The strategy implemented involved wide dissemination on the internet; academic and professional publications; presentations at relevant conferences and fairs; and liaison and where possible joint undertakings with related projects. The strategy was designed to provide effective diffusion of the project concept, ideas and results. There were a number of distinct components of the dissemination strategy, viz.,

- Management and continued development of project communication and dissemination infrastructure (website design and development, brochure, etc.) within the final year of the project.
- Achieving awareness and acceptance of the relevance of the project results in the eyes of stakeholders associated with the offshore wind energy sector, planning and regulatory agencies, etc.
- Effectively communicate and promote key project results and outputs to targeted audiences.

Figure 1 below illustrates the type of activities to be undertaken in the communication of results.

Figure 1: Overview of X-ROTOR strategies for communication, dissemination and exploitation

2 Communication tools

2.1 Website

The project website (located at the following URL: <https://xrotor-project.eu>) went live with a soft launch at the start of the project and was relaunched in the second year. The website redesign took account of the lessons from the soft launch and feedback from partners. Key elements of this specification include: Responsive website design; Mobile first approach, but cater for desktop, mobile & tablet devices; Degrade ‘gracefully’ in older browsers; Journey mapping used to optimise UX design; Compliant with all relevant data protection and any other relevant legal requirements; Compliant with Double-A standard of the Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI) Web Content Accessibility Guidelines 2.1; Pages optimised for loading speed.

The objectives of the website were to: raise awareness about the project and its objectives; communicate about the project’s research and outreach activities; promote engagement with industry and societal stakeholders; disseminate the results of the project; and acknowledge funding and support of the Horizon 2020 programme; and publicise the involvement of the participating partners (and where appropriate, individual contributors). The project website was designed and maintained using the WordPress Content Management System (CMS). A feature-rich CMS that allows the development of quite complex sites but allows non expert users to substantially maintain the site. A modern responsive web design approach was taken, meaning that the coding is such that the website is presented differently depending on the viewing device. This is so that content will be resized or hidden in accordance with the formatting and presentation layers protocols on device of different sizes *i.e.*, desktops, tablets, and smartphones. The website was initially ‘soft-launched’ with a simple layout before being revamped and redesigned (with video mock-ups of the X-ROTOR), once feedback was gathered from critical friends¹. The website has a relatively straightforward structure comprising the following: landing page, overview of the project, profile of partners, project outputs, news and events, contact details. Over the life of the project the website was updated. Many of these sections (*e.g.*, project outputs) had minimal content at the start, which was added to as the project progressed.

Figure 2: Example of web pages from the X-ROTOR web site

¹ The ideal of a critical friend is that they would be someone sympathetic to the overall goals of an undertaking, but not involved in day-to-day conduct, and so able to bring a critical distance to commenting. In this case the critical friends were predominately team members and colleagues of project partners.

2.2 Briefing Statement

To assist in explaining the X-ROTOR project to prospective interested stakeholders, an agreed overview of the project was used by partners as outlined in Text Box 1 below.

Wind power can make a significant contribution to Europe's electricity needs and in so doing contribute to achieving the EU's goal of climate neutrality. The EU proposes to increase offshore wind capacity significantly over the coming years - from its current level of 12 GW to 60 GW by 2030 and 300 GW by 2050.

However, the cost of energy from offshore wind is higher than onshore installations due to more challenging construction and maintenance conditions. X-ROTOR a research project funded under the EU Horizon 2020 programme (grant # 101007135) aims to directly address cost of energy reduction and scalability, through the developing a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time the consortium will work to increase the technology readiness level of the X-ROTOR concept, to determine its economic, social and environmental impacts and to confirm its potential for a levelised costs of energy (LCOE) reduction.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK), working with Delft University of Technology (NL), University College Cork (IE), Fundacion Cener (ES), GE Renovables España (ES), and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NO). Further information can be found on <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Text box 1: Briefing statement introducing the X-ROTOR project.

2.3 Logos

In so far as possible, and as relevant X-ROTOR used a common brand and its visual identity was communicated through use of its logo as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Project logo.

In some circumstances where a logo with minimal text was more appropriate and the alternative version shown in Figure 4 was used.

Figure 4: Project logo (with minimal text)

The funding acknowledgement & EU logo shown in Figure 5 below, was used in all communications materials.

The XROTOR Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101007135.

Figure 5: EU Logo and funding acknowledgement

2.4 Press release guidelines

A style guide was prepared detailed below in Text box 2 below was prepared as an aid for partners in the preparation of press releases.

<p>1. The Headline</p> <p>The headline should be catchy and to the point – do not try to tell the full story in the headline.</p> <p>2. The First Paragraph</p> <p>The first paragraph should summarise the story and further paragraphs should elaborate - if the opening paragraph doesn't generate interest, journalists will not read further!</p> <p>3. Further Paragraphs</p> <p>The 'middle' of a press release should pull out the most interesting aspects of story. To make it relevant to the reader, linking it to local community or connecting it to a current news story may help. Keep the language non-technical and ensure it is suitable for the general public – get non-technical colleagues to read press release to see if it makes sense.</p> <p>4. Quotes</p> <p>To make the story interesting it is vital that a quote from a local partner spokesperson be include. This should be short but also as relevant as possible. Additional quotes from the coordinator or the local stakeholders for example, may add to the release – such quotes should be cleared through University of Strathclyde first.</p> <p>5. Closing Paragraph</p> <p>The closing paragraph should be used to promote the project website https://xrotor-project.eu (and if considered appropriate in the context of the story the project twitter account @XRotorProject)</p> <p>6. End</p> <p>Mark the end of the release with the word –ends– in the centre of the page</p> <p style="text-align: center;">-ends-</p> <p>7. Contact for Further Information</p> <p>Contact details should be added to the end of the release. Include a name, phone number, email address, website link and if possible, a mobile number of the local partner contact.</p>
--

Text box 2: Style sheet for press releases

2.5 Presentation template

A template for presentation slides was designed to standardise communication while also ensuring that all presentations from the project included key items (logos, funding acknowledgement, web address etc.). Example slides based on this template are included below.

Figure 6: Project presentation template – title slide

Figure 7: Project presentation template – blank slide

2.6 Display banner poster

Figure 8 below illustrates the design of the ‘pull-up’ display banner prepared for use at the X-ROTOR project events. The banner design includes: a ‘text bite’ for the project, project logo; webpage address; images to represents the project theme; EU logo and funding acknowledgement, *etc.*

Figure 8: X-ROTOR roll-up display banner

3 Dissemination Outputs

Once research outputs started to emerge, a [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org) presence was established for the project on <https://zenodo.org/communities/x-rotor>. All project outputs are deposited in this general open access repository. Public deliverables and open access publications are freely available, while confidential deliverables have restricted access. The repository provides DOIs for documents (if required), which greatly improves the ability to cite X-ROTOR outputs making it easier to promote the research. This use of the Zenodo repository, provided through the EU OpenAire initiative, will ensure the availability of project outputs long after the project has concluded².

Figure 9: X-ROTOR Zenodo presence.

² Partners have also been encourage to utilise institutional repositories where available.

The project also had a presence on social media, specifically Twitter (or X as it become known). The account established at the start of the project (@XRotorProject) was utilised in a supporting role to other communication channels. It was used to promote the project, highlight partners and their contributions, and as a means to promote project outputs.

Towards the latter stages of the project a project YouTube channel was established as a means of sharing videography from X-ROTOR – <https://www.youtube.com/@XROTORProject>. While never intended as a major route for project communications, it does offers a means of documenting events and communicating outputs from the project.

Newsletters were prepared during focused on specific themes of the project, these were made available through the project website. The first served as an introduction to, and an over of the X-ROTOR project. The other newsletters covered a range of themes including: economic analyses, societal and human aspects, environmental aspects, technical innovations, etc.

Figure 10: X-ROTOR on Twitter/X

Figure 11: Examples of project newsletters

Conference contributions

- Leithead, W. E. (2021). X-ROTOR. *EERA JP Wind-SP4 FALCON 30/50 Workshop: Future of Aerodynamics, Loads and Control 2030-2050*. 25 February, online.
- Bensason, D. (2023) Experimental study of the X-Rotor with wingtip-mounted rotors, *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Giri Ajay, A., Morgan, L. & Simao Ferreira, C. (2023). Comparison of aerodynamic models for the X-Rotor vertical-axis wind turbine concept. *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Giri Ajay, A., & Simao Ferreira, C. (2023). Impact of vertical induction in vertical axis wind turbines *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Yazdanpanah, R., Mortazavizadeh, S. A., Anaya-Lara, O., Campos-Gaona, D. (2023). Design of rotatory transformer for wireless power transfer in the X-Rotor wind turbine. *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Muskulus, M. (2023). Structural design optimization of a jacket for the X-Rotor turbine. *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Morgan, L. (2023). Control strategy options for the X-Rotor wind turbine concept. *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Dunphy, N.P. & Lennon, B. (2023). Environmental, social and economic aspects of novel turbine design, *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Leithead, W. (2023) Overview of the X-Rotor Wind Turbine Concept. *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Carroll, J. (2023). X-ROTOR O&M and CoE Modelling. *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May, Glasgow, UK.
- Giri Ajay, A. (2022). Aerodynamic and aeroelastic analysis of an X-shaped vertical-axis wind turbine. *North American Wind Energy Academy NAWEA WindTech Conference 2022*, 20-22 September, Delaware, USA.
- Teng, Y., Anaya-Lara, O., Yazdanpanah, R., Campos-Gaona, D., Mortazavizadeh, S. A. (2023). Design and analysis of a 100kW rotary transformer for X-ROTOR wind generators. *IEEE Workshop on Electrical Machines Design, Control and Diagnosis WEMDCD 2023*, 13-14 April Newcastle, UK

- Mortazavizadeh, S. A., Yazdanpanah, R., Campos-Gaona, D. Anaya-Lara, O. (2023). Inner-Rotor and Outer-Rotor PMSG Designs for Novel Offshore Wind Turbines. *SIELMEN 2023*, 11–13 October, Chisinau Romania.
- Giri Ajay, A., Simao Ferreira, C. (2023). Numerical study of wake re-energisation of an X-shaped vertical-axis wind turbine. *North American Wind Energy Academy NAWEA WindTech Conference 2023*, 30 October – 01 November, Denver, Colorado, USA.
- Mendez, B. & Simao Ferreira, C. (2023). CFD analysis and aerodynamic models. *EERA Deepwind Conference 2023*, 18-20 January, Trondheim, Norway.
- Dong, J., Correia Da Silva, A., Muskulus, M., (2024). Pile design for X-ROTOR offshore wind turbine. *EERA Deepwind Conference 2024*, 18-20 January, Trondheim, Norway.
- Bensason, D., Ferreira, C., Sciacchitano, A. (2023). The near wake of the X-Rotor vertical axis wind turbine: an experimental study, *Wake Conference 2023*, 20-22 June, Visby, Sweden.
- Bensason, D., Carlos Ferreira, C., Andrea Sciacchitano, A. (2023). Wake re-energization of the X-Rotor vertical-axis wind turbine, *Flow Visualization Symposium*, 10-13 July, Delft, Netherlands.
- Bensason, D., Ferreira, C., Sciacchitano, A. (2023) Wake re-energization of the X-Rotor vertical-axis wind turbine. *North American Wind Energy Academy NAWEA WindTech Conference 2023*, 30 October – 01 November, Denver, Colorado, USA
- Wu, Y., Avallone, F., Ragni, D. Casalino, D. (2023). Computational study on the aeroacoustics of the X-Rotor – a hybrid vertical - horizontal axis wind turbine. *10th International Conference on Wind Turbine Noise*, 21–23 June, Dublin, Ireland.
- Méndez, B., Pires, O., Bretos, D. (2023). X-ROTOR disruptive wind turbine advanced aerodynamic analysis using CFD. *EERA Deepwind Conference 2024*, 18-20 January, Trondheim, Norway.
- Mortazavizadeh, S. A., Yazdanpanah, R., Campos-Gaona, D. Anaya-Lara, O., (2024). Power-train design for XROTOR wind turbine including wireless power transmission and multi-level DAB converters. *EERA Deepwind Conference 2024*, 18–20 January, Trondheim, Norway.
- Morgan L., Giri Ajay, A., Leithead W. (2023). Investigation into the effect of tilt angles for vertical axis wind turbines. *Wind Energy Science Conference WESC 2023*, 23-26 May Glasgow, UK.
- Recalde-Camacho, L., Morgan, L., Kazemi-Amiri, A., Leithead, W. (2024). Controller design for the X-Rotor Offshore Wind Turbine Concept. *Torque 2024*, 29–31 May, Florence, Italy.
- Correia da Silva, A. & Muskulus, M. (2023). VAWT support structure preliminary mass sensitivity due to aerodynamic load scaling. *EERA Deepwind Conference 2023*. 17-19 January, Trondheim, Norway.

Journal publications

At the time of writing the following open access peer reviewed journal articles have been published arising from work within the X-ROTOR project.

- McMorland, J., Flannigan, C., Carroll, J., Collu, M., McMillan, D., Leithead, W., & Coraddu, A. (2022). A review of operations and maintenance modelling with considerations for novel wind turbine concepts. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 165, 112581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112581>

- Morgan, L., & Leithead, W. (2022). Aerodynamic modelling of a novel vertical axis wind turbine concept. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2257(1), 012001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2257/1/012001>
- Flannigan, C., Carroll, J., & Leithead, W. (2022). Operations expenditure modelling of the X-Rotor offshore wind turbine concept. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2265(3), 032054. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2265/3/032054>
- Bensason, D., Sciacchitano, A., & Ferreira, C. (2023). Near wake of the X-Rotor vertical-axis wind turbine. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2505(1), 012040. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2505/1/012040>
- Pérez Caballero, L. M., Neira D'Angelo, F., Tschentscher, R., Gottschalk, A., Salem, A. M., Carbonell, D., Dudita-Kauffeld, M., Bruch, A., Alamaro, E., Pasquini, L., Ceroni, P., Grozdanova, A., Privitera, S., Vermang, B., Schulz, P., Mencarelli, D., Pierantoni, L., Midrio, M., Leithead, W., ... Kauffeld, M. (2023). Developing the next generation of renewable energy technologies: an overview of low-TRL EU-funded research projects. *Open Research Europe*, 3, 8. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.15276.2>
- Silva, A. C. da, & Muskulus, M. (2023). VAWT support structure mass sensitivity due to aerodynamic load scaling. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2626(1), 012003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2626/1/012003>
- Dong, J., Silva, A. C. Da, & Muskulus, M. (2023). Pile design for X-rotor offshore wind turbine. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2626(1), 012004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2626/1/012004>
- Giri Ajay, A., Morgan, L., Wu, Y., Bretos, D., Cascales, A., Pires, O., & Ferreira, C. (2024). Aerodynamic model comparison for an X-shaped vertical-axis wind turbine. *Wind Energy Science*, 9(2), 453–470. <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-9-453-2024>

Other Journal Articles

In addition to the above listed articles, an additional three articles are under review (journals such as) and a further five articles are in preparation. The target journals for these articles include Wind Energy Science, Wiley Wind Energy, Renewable Energy, and Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization. An list of X-ROTOR journal publications (which will be kept updated) can be found on the project's Zenodo listing of [articles](#).

Participation in Trade fairs

X-ROTOR representatives attended several trade fairs and exhibitions as part of ongoing engagement with the wider wind energy community.

- Wind Energy Ireland Trade Show, October 2023 (Dublin, IE)
- WindEurope Conference & Exhibition, April 2023 (Copenhagen, DK)
- HUSUM Wind, September 2023 (Husum, DE)
- WindEurope Conference & Exhibition, March 2024 (Bilbao, ES)

Attending these trade fairs enable the project team to engage industry actors about X-ROTOR and collect information to feed into the project.

Figure 12: Exhibition floor Husum Wind trade fair, Husum Germany.

Mini-symposia

Three X-ROTOR mini-symposia organised as official components of major research conferences, as a means to promote the work of the project and disseminate emerging results. In January 2023, an X-ROTOR mini-symposium was organised during EERA DeepWind 2023 conference in Trondheim, Norway. While in May 2023, a second X-ROTOR mini-symposium was organised during the Wind Energy Science Conference 2023 held in Glasgow, United Kingdom.

Final Project Event

On 21 March 2024, a final project dissemination mini-symposium was organised as an official side event of the WindEurope Annual Event³, held in Bilbao, Spain. A variety of stakeholders were invited to the event from across the value chain. This event provided an opportunity for the project team to present the work completed within the X-ROTOR project and the results arising.

The seminar was structured into two segments. A high-level overview of the projects results was provided in the morning session, while an afternoon session was dedicated to the presentation of more detailed information of the X-ROTOR concept through both oral and poster presentations.

Figure 13: Images from the X-ROTOR final event at WindEurope

³ WindEurope is a Brussels-based association promoting the use of wind power in Europe. It organises an annual three-day wind energy conference and exhibition, which covers both on- and offshore wind energy. The event's multiple conference sessions, hundreds of speakers, and 500+ exhibitors attract in excess of 12,000 attendees each year.